

A PRAGMATIC APPROACH TO CULTURAL DIFFERENCES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH MAGAZINE ADVERTISING

Khudoyberdiyeva Lola Utanazarovna

Termez State University, 1st year master's degree in Linguistics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6480897>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th April 2022

Accepted: 15th April 2022

Online: 20th April 2022

KEY WORDS

Content analysis,
pragmatics, intelligence
and tickling advertising,
localization, variables,
persuasion, courtesy,
magazines, advertising
culture, cultural metrics

ABSTRACT

Many American companies that want to increase their sales and achieve their growth goals to expand their opportunities to deliver their products to other countries. However, on a global scale, measurement often requires a lot of trial and error when English-speaking companies try to market their tokens. To facilitate this process, localization specialists are often hired. To make ads more culturally relevant, it is possible to "localize" or change them. Since the area of localization is relatively new, the research is of the extent to which poor advertising is localized. The purpose of this article is to examine the cultural differences between advertising.

Advertising-information about the quality of tokens, the profit from their purchase; special information distributed about legal entities and individuals or products for the purpose of obtaining direct or indirect profit (income). Advertising is considered a component of marketing and affects the formation of demand and consumer tastes. For example, ads are considered to have a different form, appearance and purpose. Especially if we look at ads in European or Uzbek newspapers and magazines, and of course if we compare them, we can see cultural differences between them. Through advertising worked pictures, too, each state shows its own culture. For example, through Uzbek national clothes, patterns, design, historical places, dates, figures, great figures, colors or special holidays,

advertisements on national grounds are created.

Advertising is carried out for the purpose of creating the image of the enterprise (long-term impact), increasing the current sales volume (short-term impact), helping buyers to decide what to buy and why it is necessary to buy, and for other purposes. The main task of advertising is to interest the buyer, so as not to lose the customer buyers and focus on them widen. Two different samples of the printed magazine were taken to identify ads from beauty magazines published in Uzbekistan and America. The more localization in the mass media of Uzbekistan, the more different advertising strategies of Uzbekistan and the United States for comparison, non-local Uzbek advertising and localized advertising are included in the framework of coded

advertising for different pragmatic characteristics. The results are then localized analysis through content analysis and square statistics to find out what the pragmatic characteristics and non-native Uzbek ads are. Research has shown that non-localized Uzbek advertising pays more attention to substantive persuasion strategies. The most important thing is to confirm the celebrities and an extensive list of reasons to buy a particular product. Localized Russian advertising, on the contrary, is based on more scarcity. In particular, persuasion tactics, such as metaphor and implication, are used. 80% of localized Uzbek ads had no change in the advertising text from the English version of the ads, which means that the level of localization in Uzbek advertising was currently low. Localization and different persuasion techniques are needed between the two samples.

Pragmatics is the study of how communicative messages, context, speaker intent, and receiver understand all interrelations in a particular situation. When communicating with a person, someone else, the message of that person, will have both denotative meanings (through a strict interpretation of what the words mean, that is, the dictionary) and the connotative meaning (how words can be, is interpreted through the details and context of the situation). From a pragmatic point of view for the study of a message, there are several accepted theories used for the analysis pragmatics are the definitions given. Co-operative principle, this is regulated by a set of principles that act as norms for improve each conversation. People usually try to maximize the exchange of information. According to the communication and cooperative principle,

there are four principles that can help with this.

Linguistic choices that people make to influence the situation can be classified as positive. Tactful strategies (expressing negativity) and negative tactile strategies (increasing the distance between the speaker and receiver to maintain the status). In advertising, ads often come into force. Both positive and negative politely strategies will be preserved in the consumer agency, act as a request to buy the product even in advertisements, to help consumers feel.

The term "localization" is claimed by various fields, such as economics, medicine and biology, expressing different meanings and concepts. However, in general, "localization" can be described as follows. For example, "the act or reality of turning something into a local character or adapting something to a local audience or market." Within the framework of linguistics, the concept of "localization" is actually possible.

The globalization process is generally used in the context of sales and marketing, that is, it is a process in which a company breaks free in the home markets to continue its business opportunities. Localization is not translated, the process of "global replacement" for the word. This is precisely the meaning of the source material on the target language with particular emphasis on the cultural required to convey the total. Thus, localization is a process that includes, in addition to the lexical translation of the text. Each component of the given message was received by a new audience, taking into account the cultural impact of how it was. The question of the necessity of some localization in the business world is really

so different from cultures. To be successful, does advertising have to go through the localization process?

Based on the sources, the components for reliable advertising are as follows:

1. It is necessary to pay attention to itself.
2. He must keep the interest he attracts.
3. It should be remembered, or recognize that any rate is familiar. (Souvenir)
4. This should require proper action. (Sales force)

These same pragmatic characteristics, identified mainly by the indicated sources, are the basis for the analysis from the advertising purpose to its function. The importance of advertising services in the conditions of the market economy getting improve advertisement is increasing the contribution of advertising costs in the handling costs. Advertising becomes a separate network of entrepreneurship and advertising is organized in accordance with special rules and laws. Legality, accuracy, reliability, harm to the user from advertising, as well as the use of forms and means that do not cause moral harm are the main requirements for advertising. Relations related to the preparation and distribution of advertising in Uzbekistan are regulated by the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on advertising" of 25 December, 1998 and the resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to this law, the dissemination of misleading or vague information that distracts consumers, as well as the promotion of certain goods or spheres of activity, is prohibited by law.

In general, the role of advertising on a variety of topics that are given in countries around the world that are more prestigious and have a much larger audience, in particular American television channels, news and newspapers and magazines, is significant. Through them, basically, large media like this have their own main source of income. In terms of development and large material income, we understand the media such as New York Times, Fox News, financial times, CCN TV channel, BBC, NBC, Euro news as the main example. Today, many private TV Channels, TV channels and Internet publications are also operating in Uzbekistan. Their main source of income is of course based on advertising. The more subscribers of this informative resource, the more his income and the companies that want to advertise to him, the more so.

The situation in the world has caused enterprises to look for new and effective methods in customer relations. The priority is not only focused on consumption and costs, but today marketing is in a position to foster a real relationship with real people. Contactless marketing should not be confused with Internet marketing, because it is simply not doing business in the global network. Contactless marketing is the establishment of a level of relationship with customers just like in real life, only in a more convenient and actual form for the modern world.

In conclusion, each state first of all has its own traditions, culture and a specific history. Therefore, the National, which has been formed for many years and has not lost its relevance, is also reflected in advertising, and the popularity of such advertising will be even easier. Especially

the result that they give is also definitely distinguished by its yield. Often, if we focus on ads in English newspaper and magazines, we will notice their culture. I know that modernity, distinctive design and creative approach are definitely one of

the aspects that must be studied. I think that advertising, based on the traditions and culture of both nations, has always justified itself and brings a profit with a good result.

References:

1. Abdullayeva Sh., Nosirov P., Marketing — bozor iqtisodiyoti asosi, T., 1994.y
2. The cultural impact of advertising - The Earthbound Report. <https://earthbound.report/2011/10/26/the-trouble-with-advertising-2/amp/>
3. Culture in Advertising. <https://www.commisceo-global.com/blog/culture-in-advertising>
4. (PDF) Culture in advertising and advertising in culture: Communication, translation, representation. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322413106_Culture_in_advertising_and_advertising_in_culture_Communication_translation_representation
5. Kontaktsiz marketing: tajriba va asliyat ahamiyati | LG O'zbekiston. <https://www.lg.com//uz/about-lg/press-and-media/untact-marketing>